

Potentiometric Determination of Dissociation Constants of HSO_4^- Ion in Dioxane-Water Media

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With the cell $\text{Pt, H}_2 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{HCl}(m_1) \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4(m_2) \\ \text{in H}_2\text{O}(x) \text{ Dioxane}(y) \end{array} \right\} \text{AgCl, Ag}$

the dissociation constants of HSO_4^- in dioxane-water media (20%, 40% and 60% wt. percent of dioxane) have been determined at different temperatures. ΔF° , ΔH° and ΔS° have been calculated.

The measurement of the second dissociation constant of sulfuric acid by potentiometric method may be traced back to Hamer¹ who used cell of the type :

$$\text{Pt, H}_2 | \text{NaHSO}_4(m_1) \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4(m_2) \text{NaCl}(m_3) | \text{AgCl, Ag.}$$

In order to eliminate the error in such determinations due to the formation of NaSO_4^- species, Davies, Jones and Monk² and later Nair and Nancollas³ determined the dissociation constant of HSO_4^- ion using the cell,

$$\text{Pt, H}_2 | \text{HCl}(m_1) \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(m_2) | \text{AgCl, Ag.}$$

The thermodynamic dissociation constant was calculated by successive approximation. The enthalpy and entropy values given by Nair and Nancollas agree well with the calorimetric values of Pitzer⁴.

In the present determination similar cell,

$$\text{Pt, H}_2 | \text{HCl}(m_1) \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(m_2) \text{H}_2\text{O}(x) \text{Dioxane}(y) | \text{AgCl, Ag,}$$

has been used. The e.m.f. of this cell is related to the hydrogen ion concentration m_{H} by the equation

$$-\log m_{\text{H}} = (E - E^\circ) / 2 \cdot 3026 \text{ RT/F} - 2 \log \gamma_{\pm} + \log m_1 \quad \dots (1)$$

where γ_{\pm} is the mean molal activity coefficient. The concentration of HSO_4^- ion is given by

$$[\text{HSO}_4^-] = m_1 + 2m_2 - m_{\text{H}^+} \quad \dots (2)$$

the ionic strength 'I' is equal to

$$m_1 + (1 + 2\alpha')m_2 \quad \dots (3)$$

1. W. J. Hamer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 860.
2. C. W. Davies, H. W. Jones and C. B. Monk, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, **48**, 921.
3. V. S. K. Nair and G. H. Nancollas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4144.
4. K. S. Pitzer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 2365.

where α' is the degree of dissociation of HSO_4^- ion and the dissociation constant for the second stage of dissociation of H_2SO_4 acid by the equation

$$K_2 \approx m_{\text{H}^+} m_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}/m_{\text{HSO}_4^-} \cdot \gamma_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}} \quad \dots (4)$$

assuming the activity coefficients of the same valence type ions are the same. The activity coefficient is calculated using Davies equation. Through successive approximation the value of K_2 is calculated for each ionic strength. A more accurate estimate of the thermodynamic dissociation constant is made by extrapolating $\log K_2$ against ionic strength to zero.

The above method of calculation is applicable upto about 40 wt % of dioxane above which the ion-association of HCl has to be taken into consideration as is apparent from the work of Marshall and Grunwald⁵. Above 45 wt % of dioxane in dioxane-water medium, we have for HCl the equilibrium

$$(1-\alpha)m_1 \quad \alpha m_1 \quad \alpha m_1$$

where K is the dissociation constant. In order to evaluate the degree of dissociation of HCl, α , the dissociation of bisulfate ion is neglected so that the concentration of hydrogen ion in the solution is given by $m_{\text{H}^+} = m_2 + \alpha m_1$, and the concentration of chloride ion m_{Cl^-} is given by $m_{\text{Cl}^-} = \alpha m_1$. Assuming $\gamma_{\text{H}^+} = \gamma_{\text{Cl}^-} = \gamma$; and $\gamma_{\text{HCl}} = 1$, we have,

$$K = \frac{(m_2 + \alpha m_1) + \alpha m_1}{(1-\alpha)m_1} \gamma^2 \quad \dots (5)$$

From equation (5), α can be evaluated. The activity coefficients of the individual ions are obtained with the help of Davies equation, using an approximate value of the ionic strength from the equation

$$I = \alpha m_1 + (1 + 2\alpha')m_2$$

making the tentative assumptions :

$$\alpha = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha' = 0$$

This value of α may then be utilised to calculate the hydrogen ion concentration of the medium from the e.m.f. values of the cell

given by the equation,

$$-\log m_{\text{H}} = \frac{E - E^\circ}{2.3026 \frac{RT}{F}} + \log \alpha m_1 + 2 \log \gamma_{\pm} \quad \dots (6)$$

Equation (6) is nothing but equation (1) except that an additional term, α , has been introduced to correct the concentration of the chloride ion for the association of HCl in solvents enriched in dioxane content.

This value of m_H will give the concentration of the bisulfate ion with the help of the equation (2) and hence another value for the ionic strength may be found using equation (3). This value of the ionic strength may then be utilised to calculate γ , α , m_H and consequently α' . This process is repeated until the ionic strength obtained in this manner becomes constant. Then the dissociation constant (K_2) of the bisulfate ion, HSO_4^- is evaluated with the help of equation (4).

EXPERIMENTAL

Dioxane was purified in the manner as described earlier⁶. Hydrochloric and sulphuric acids were of analytical reagent quality. Double distilled water was used.

Hydrogen electrode : The hydrogen electrode consisted of a platinum foil of thickness of about 0.04 mm and of area 1 sq. mm. The electrodes were platinised by the method of Ives and Hill⁷. Hydrogen gas from the cylinder was used after purification as suggested by Bates⁸.

The Silver Silver chloride electrodes were prepared by thermo-electrolytic method as described by Bates.

The hydrogen electrode compartment was a pear-shaped vessel with seven mouths (with ground-glass joints). Two of these were used for hydrogen inlets and two for two hydrogen electrodes. This vessel was joined to a vessel that had two Ag, AgCl electrodes. The arrangement provided a scope for measurements in quadruplicate. The e.m.f. measurements were taken at three different temperatures in an air thermostat with control better than $\pm 0.05^\circ$ with a L.N. K_2 potentiometer and were reproducible within ± 0.1 mv.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The measured e.m.f. readings were corrected to that for standard 1 atmosphere pressure of hydrogen using the vapour pressures of dioxane water system at different temperatures reported by Hovorka Schaefer and Dreisbach⁹. $E^\circ_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$'s in dioxane-water media at different temperatures needed in the calculation were taken from the work of Harned and co-workers¹⁰. Because of the uncertainty of $E^\circ_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ in 82 wt % of dioxane-water media, although measurements in the present work were taken in 82 wt % dioxane media, no calculation of K_2 in the medium was possible. As such the results have not been reported. The dissociation constants of HCl in media containing more than 45 wt % of dioxane have been taken from the work of Marshall and Grunwald. Because of the large uncertainty in the result, the dissociation constant of HCl has been taken the same over the temperature range. The results are given in Tables I, II and III.

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TABLE I

Cell : Pt, H₂ | HCl(m₁), H₂SO₄(m₂), Dioxane(X) H₂O (100-X) | AgCl, Ag.
20% Dioxane (w/w)

	Temp. °C						
10 ³ × m ₁		7.17	4.96	9.93	15.00	19.86	24.82
10 ³ × m ₂		6.74	5.00	9.50	10.00	15.00	20.00
<i>E</i> (volts)	25	0.44573	0.46373	0.43168	0.41566	0.40203	0.38993
	30	0.44648	0.46455	0.43188	0.41572	0.40173	0.39003
	35	0.44751	0.46558	0.43184	0.41565	0.40144	0.38949
	25	13.7	9.8	19.3	24.7	34.5	44.5
<i>I</i> × 10 ³	30	13.8	9.9	19.3	24.7	34.5	44.3
	35	13.7	9.8	19.3	24.6	34.5	44.5
	25	2.80	2.82	2.80	2.80	2.80	2.75
<i>pK</i> ₂ = -log <i>K</i> ₂	30	2.90	3.00	2.90	2.90	2.95	2.90
	35	2.97	3.14	2.99	2.98	2.98	2.95

TABLE II

Cell : Pt, H₂ | HCl(m₁), H₂SO₄(m₂), Dioxane(X) H₂O (100-X) | AgCl, Ag.
40% Dioxane (w/w)

	Temp. °C						
10 ³ × m ₁		5.12	7.17	10.24	20.48	25.40	24.70
10 ³ × m ₂		5.18	6.74	9.85	15.55	20.95	20.10
<i>E</i> (volts)	25	0.43640	0.42245	0.40654	0.37714	0.36785	0.36903
	30	0.43475	0.42044	0.40430	0.37473	0.36490	0.36625
	35	0.43465	0.41989	0.40266	0.37250	0.36210	0.36335
	25	10.10	13.70	19.80	35.10	45.20	44.90
<i>I</i> × 10 ³	30	10.26	13.91	20.10	35.90	46.24	44.70
	35	10.27	14.00	19.97	35.89	46.20	44.80
	25	3.95	4.06	4.16	3.92	4.00	4.06
<i>pK</i> ₂	30	4.06	4.15	4.30	4.19	4.11	4.18
	35	4.10	4.23	4.45	4.32	4.26	4.16

TABLE III

Cell : $\text{Pt, H}_2 | \text{HCl}(m_1), \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(m_2) \text{ Dioxane}(X) \text{ H}_2\text{O} (100-X) | \text{AgCl, Ag.}$
 60% Dioxane (w/w)

	Temp. °C						
$10^3 \times m_1$		10.00	11.50	13.42	13.42	13.42	15.00
$10^3 \times m_2$		10.00	8.72	8.72	10.46	12.20	15.00
E (volt)	27	0.36447	0.36197	0.35742	0.35630	0.35387	0.34925
	32	0.36135	0.35966	0.35270	0.35136	0.35081	0.34546
	37	0.35495	0.35095	0.34710	0.34515	0.34465	0.33965
$I \times 10^3$	27	18.3	17.8	18.9	20.6	23.7	27.2
	32	18.6	18.5	20.0	21.7	23.6	27.8
	37	18.7	18.6	20.2	21.9	23.7	27.9
pK_2	27	4.64	4.62	4.56	4.58	4.60	4.57
	32	4.66	4.71	4.74	4.72	4.78	4.70
	37	4.88	4.72	4.81	4.84	4.90	4.77

The pK_2 values for different percentage of dioxane and at different temperatures have been plotted against ionic strength and extrapolated to zero to get the thermodynamic pK_2 . It may be mentioned that consideration of all the limitations in the approximations used in the calculations in the different stages, discussed earlier might lead to values (numbers) having a maximum uncertainty of ± 0.2 pK units in case of results for medium containing 60% by weight of dioxane. The pK_2 values are given in Table IV. The pK_2 values at different temperatures have also been determined by spectrophotometric method in our laboratory. These have also been included in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Percentage of Dioxane (w/w)	Temp. °C	pK_2						
		20°	25°	27°	30°	32°	35°	37°
	$\frac{1 \times 10^6}{4.576T}$	74.58	73.30	72.84	72.10	71.69	70.90	69.03
20	(i)	2.98	3.03	—	3.10	—	3.20	—
	(ii)	—	2.86	—	2.96	—	3.05	—
40	(i)	4.08	4.12	—	4.20	—	4.26	—
	(ii)	—	4.06	—	4.15	—	4.23	—
60	(ii)	—	4.53	4.60	—	4.72	—	4.82

Note : (i) pK_2 values determined by spectrophotometric method.
 (ii) pK_2 values determined by potentiometric method.

TABLE V

Percentage of Dioxane	Temp. °C	ΔF° Kcals mole ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\circ$ at 25° cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\circ$ (Kcals mole ⁻¹)	
				(i)	(ii)
0	25°	2.7	26.0	5.2	—
	25°	3.9			
	30°	4.1	34.2	6.2	6.3
20	35°	4.3			
	25°	5.5			
	30°	5.7	42.6	7.0	7.2
40	35°	6.0			
	27°	6.31			
	32°	6.60	48.0 (27°C)	—	8.0
60	37°	6.80			

Note: (i) Calculated from the spectrophotometric results.

(ii) Calculated from the potentiometric results.

The thermodynamic quantities, such as the change of enthalpy of the reaction ΔH° , the free energy change ΔF° and the change of entropy, ΔS° , have been computed from the dissociation constants at different temperatures. These are given in Table V. The values for the same in aqueous medium are included for comparison. The ΔH° value has been taken from the calorimetric measurement by Pitzer⁴. The value of ΔF° has been calculated using the pK_2 value given by Young, Klotz and Singleterry¹¹. ΔF° , $-\Delta H^\circ$ and $-\Delta S^\circ$ are found to increase as the percentage of dioxane increases in the mixed media.

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